

A Study on Factors Influencing Tourist Visiting Mandalay

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Abstract: The objective of this study is to explore the factors effecting to the tourists to visit Mandalay and to analysis the most influencing factors that the tourist to come Mandalay. The descriptive research method was applied in this study. This study depends on two main data sources, such as: primary data and secondary data. Primary data are collected by interviewing with 194 international visitors through a structured questionnaire, designed to obtain information of the tourist during their visit in Mandalay at the departure of Mandalay International Airport. For the secondary data, annual reports from (2012) to (2015) prepared by Ministry of Hotels and Tourism (MOHT) and Directorate of Hotel and Tourism (DHT) are used as sources. Moreover, newspapers, previous research paper, relevant books and internet website are also used as sources. There were four factors that influencing visitors on Mandalay and measured by: Environmental Factors, Socio- Economic Factors, Cultural Factors and Religious Factors. The study found that the cultural factor is the most influencing factors for the visitors who visited Mandalay.

Keywords: Tourism management; Tourism development; Sustainable tourism

1. Introduction

In many countries, developed and developing steadily the tourism industry, providing employment millions of people and interacting with almost all sectors of the economy. Today, tourism on gross income is the second largest in the world after oil and the largest in the world to provide jobs. Besides, it is the largest industry in the world in terms of gross revenues and foreign exchange earnings.

There are four factors that affect to tourists to visit new destination; environmental factor, socio-economic factors, historical and cultural factors and religious factors. Mandalay is the second-largest city in Myanmar and situated in the hot and dry central region of the country. Surrounded by other ancient royal capitals, including Sagaing, Ava (Inwa) and Amarapura. In Mandalay, visitors can watch traditional handicrafts being made, such as tapestries, marionettes, bronze items and stone and wood carvings. Mandalay also houses the most revered Buddha statue in the country, the MahaMyat Muni image. Early Another interesting attraction is Kuthodaw Pagoda (also called the largest book in the world), built by King Mindon after the Fifth Buddhist Council, where he decided to inscribe the entire Buddhist Canon on 729 marble slabs. Mandalay has excellent air, road and river connections to all parts of Myanmar. Another interesting sightseeing point in the city is the 230-metre Mandalay Hill.

Although most sites all over Myanmar can attract tourists, implementation of tasks for tourism development is still weak. If we overlook in the real situation of improvement and satisfaction of the tourists in Mandalay, there are some improvements starting from recent year because the Tourism Development strategy by government and to attract the tourist for repeat visits.

A tourist's ever-changing expectations that business owners and employees must understand. By understanding the factors such as environmental factor, economic factor, historical factor, cultural factor and religious factor, the stakeholder related with tourism can not only maintain the tourist arrival in Mandalay but also can give quality service.

1.1 Rational of the Study

Tourism denotes the temporary and short-term movement of people to destination outside the place where they normally live and work. Tourism as an invisible export has become a major item in foreign trade. Some developing countries are largely dependent on tourism while other obtains a good percentage of their export earnings from Tourism. Still others including Myanmar are trying to attract as many tourists as possible.

The political change in Myanmar is one of the factors for tourist attraction of Myanmar. Myanmar tourism is now implementing to develop by making necessary plans and arrangements for the development

of the country as a world-renowned tourist destination. Mandalay is very important destination for them. Besides, there are some improvements starting for recent year.

1.2 Objective of the Study

The overall objective of this thesis is an attempt to render help in the promotion of Myanmar' Tourism, especially in Mandalay. Accordingly, the following objectives are adopted: 1. To explore the current situation of tourism development in Mandalay. 2. To analysis the most influencing factors that the tourist to come Mandalay

1.3 Scope and Method of the Study

The scope of this thesis is to assess to current situation of Myanmar Tourism Industry and analyzed the factors on influencing the tourist who coming to Mandalay. Primary data are collected by interviewing with 194 international visitors through a structured questionnaire, designed to obtain information of the tourist during their visit in Mandalay at the departure of Mandalay International Airport.

For the secondary data, annual reports from (2012) to (2015) prepared by Ministry of Hotels and Tourism (MOHT) and Directorate of Hotel and Tourism (DHT) are used as sources. Moreover, newspapers, previous research paper, relevant books and internet website are also used as sources.

1.4 Organization of the Study

This thesis consists of five chapters. Chapter (1) is Introduction sections, objective of the study expected outcome, scope and method of the study and organization of the study. Theoretical background of the paper is described in Chapter (2). Chapter (3) is occupied by the overview of tourism industry in Mandalay. Chapter (4) presents about the analysis of influencing factors the tourist to visit Mandalay. Chapter (5) is a conclusion section including extracted finding and suggestions.

2. Theoretical Background of Tourism

This chapter presents the theoretical background of the tourism. It is divided into four sections. The first section describes the definition of the tourism and the second one is various type of the tourism. The third part is about buying decision process and the main factors are presented in the last section of the chapter.

2.1 Definition of Tourism

Tourism is an activity done by an individual or a group of individuals, which leads to a motion from a place to another. From a country to another for performing a specific task or it is a visit to a place or several places in the purpose of entertaining which leads to an awareness of other civilizations and cultures, also increasing the knowledge of countries, cultures, and history.

Tourism has a direct impact on the national revenue for all touristic countries, it creates work opportunities, industries, and several investments to serve and raise nations performance and cultures, also distributes their history, civilization, and traditions. Tourism is a dynamic and competitive industry that requires the ability to adapt constantly to customers' changing needs and desires, as the customer's satisfaction, safety and enjoyment are particularly the focus of tourism businesses.

2.2 Types of Tourism

There are many ways to define the type of Tourism. The diverse tourism types are created from the experiences that tourists want to experiences; such as the cases of the nature tourism, cultural tourism, adventure tourism, and etc. Each type of tourism is a way to give a denomination to a new market niche for a different experience. The figure (2.1) shows the overview of tourism classification. There are two types of tourism (1) mass tourism, and (2) alternative tourism

Mass Tourism: Mass Tourism or Traditional Tourism generally refers to the big conglomerates or tourist resorts in the world. Mass tourism is group travel to a destination for purposes of leisure.

Alternative Tourism: Alternative Tourism is defined as not being Mass Tourism. Some researches defined alternative tourism as “a tourism that gives emphasis to the contact and understanding between the hosts and the tourist, as well as the environment” (Smith & Eadington, 1992). Also, as a tourism that is consistent with the natural, social and community values and that allows a positive relationship among locals and tourists (Wearing & Neil. 1999).

2.3 Model of Consumer Decision-Making Framework

Gilbert (1991) suggested a model for consumer decision-making in which is shown in Figure 2.10. This model suggests that there are two levels of factors that have an effect on the consumer. The first level of influences is close to the person and includes psychological influence such as perception and learning. The second level of influences includes those, which have been developed during the socialization process and include reference groups and family influences. All these models that have been adapted for tourism offer some into the consumer behavior process involved during the purchase post-purchase decision stages.

2.4 Four factors influencing tourist visiting to choice destination

Important factors that affect the development of tourism are as follows:

2.4.1 Environmental factors: Two main environmental factors that have led to the growth of tourism:

1) Good climate: Good climate is one of the most important features of attraction for any tourist place.

2) Beautiful scenery: Tourism booms at picnic spots with beautiful sceneries. For example, sunrise and sunset points, long sea beaches, fresh water lakes, waterfalls, etc., often attract large numbers of tourists.

2.4.2 Socio-economic factors: Four important socio-economic factors that influence the development of tourism:

1) Accessibility: Of all socio-economic factors, accessibility is the most important one. All tourist centers must be easily accessible by various modes of transportation like roads, railways, air and water.

2) Accommodation: Places of tourists' interest must be capable enough to provide good accommodation and catering facilities. A type of accommodation required by tourists depends on their lives-styles, standard of living, capacity to spend money, nature of services expected, etc.

3) Amenities: Growth of tourism at a particular place is also influenced crucial factors like; how well the site is maintained for touring activities like skiing, roping, paragliding, rowing, fishing, surfing, safari adventure, etc. Whether emergency facilities are available or not, so on.

4) Ancillary services: If a tour destination is equipped by ancillary (supplementary) services like banking and finance, the Internet and telecom connectivity, hospitals, insurance, so on, then such a place succeeds to hold (retain) more tourists for a longer time. This overall helps to boost the local economy to some extent.

2.4.3 Historical and cultural factors

Many tourists are attracted to places of historical significance and that which have a legacy of rich cultural heritage. People love and enjoy exploring destinations where there are famous ancient monuments, marvelous forts, castles and palaces of earlier kings and queens, etc.

Examples: Taj Mahal in India, Nazca lines and Machu Picchu in Peru, Pyramid of Giza in Egypt, Great wall of China and Stonehenge in England.

2.4.4. Religious factors

People often make pilgrims to places of religious importance to seek inner peace, get blessing of their favorite deities and gurus, attain salvation before death, etc. Here, faiths, beliefs and sentiments of people contribute in booming tourism at holy places. Examples of places that are well-known for their religious significance are Jerusalem in Israel, Mecca and Medina in Saudi Arabia, Varanasi and Amritsar in India, etc.

2.4.5 Other factors

Sometimes other factors also contribute toward growth of tourism at unexpected places. Research activities and adventures of deep seas and caves, geological studies of hot-water springs and geysers,

seismic analysis of active volcanoes, investigation of paranormal-activities in abandoned ghost towns, etc. also contribute in developing tourism on some scale.

3. Overview of Tourism Industry in Mandalay

This chapter firstly explain about the four' s factors of Mandalay such as: (1) Environmental factors of Mandalay, (2) Socio-Economic factors of Mandalay, (3) Cultural factors of Mandalay and (4) Religious factors of Mandalay. This section also includes tourism development in Mandalay.

3.1 Environmental factors of Mandalay

Mandalay is located in the central dry zone of Burma by the Irrawaddy River at 21.98° north, 96.08° east, 80 meters (260 feet) above sea level. Mandalay is situated on the eastern banks of the Ayeyarwaddy River in Central Myanmar, 668 Km north of Yangon. It has a tropical wet and dry climate. Average temperatures in January, the coolest month, hovers around 21 ° C while the warmest month, April, averages 31 ° C. Mandalay is very hot in the months of April and May, with average high temperatures easily exceeding 35 ° C. A 2010 estimate by the UN puts Mandalay' s population at more than 1 million.

3.2 Socio-Economic factors of Mandalay

Mandalay is commercial center with rail, road, river and air linkages to all parts of the Union of Myanmar. Mandalay is 668 km north of Yangon and easily accessible. Myanmar Airway, Yangon Airway, Air Mandalay, Air KbZ operate daily flights on hours from Yangon. It takes about 8 hours by Express coaches and about 14 hours by Train from Yangon. The city is connected to other parts of the country and to China and India and Thailand by multiple modes of transportation. According to the survey by MMRD, 46% of the respondents rated their future of industry as good prospect due to increasing market demand, FDI partner and better infrastructure and services. Most potential sectors include hotel and tourism, manufacturing and trading.

3.3 Cultural factors of Mandalay

Mandalay is historically known as the last royal capital of the Myanmar Kingdom. It also is known as Yatanabon- Naypyidaw (meaning Gem City), Mandalay was founded by King Mindon in 1885. The city was named after the Mandalay Hill, which is situated at the northeast corner of the present city. The city is now almost 150 years old and it is the country' s third largest city; the cultural heart of Myanmar where the most refined arts, traditions of dance, music and drama live on. Mandalay is well known for its traditional arts and crafts, wood, marble and stone carvings, gold and silver crafts, hand-woven silk and tapestries. As Mandalay is being the last Myanmar kingdom, there are so many places that can reflect the history of the past. Attraction places in Myanmar are mostly

occupied with pagodas, monasteries, and some historical places. Some of the most popular destination areas are: Kuthodaw pagoda, Mahamuni image, Mandalay Hill, U-Bein Bridge, Mandalay Palace, Atumashi monastery, Sandamuni pagodas, and golden palace monastery. Mandalay today is a striking phenomenon composed of modern and classic images with the ancient cultural beauty of the royal palace and the moat surrounding it, and the natural impressionistic beauty of the Mandalay Hill, harmoniously added with new architectural phonography of modern houses and brick buildings.

3.4 Religious factors of Mandalay

Mandalay is the religious center of Buddhism, having numerous monasteries and more than 700 pagodas. Mandalay has a lot of pilgrims and holy places. It is not all pagoda. Mandalay has several churches, India temples and mosques among the many temples. At the foot of Mandalay Hill sits the world's official "Buddhist Bible", also known as the world's largest book, in Kuthodaw Pagoda. The styles of Mandalay Buddha Images and Buddha Statues were many since King Mandon . There are 729 slabs of stone that together are inscribed with the entire Pāli canon, each housed in its own white stupa. 60 % of Monks live in Mandalay. Mandalay is also the center of Buddhist teaching monastery.

3.5 Tourism Development in Mandalay

Tourism has become an important source of income for most of the countries of the world. Worldwide, international tourist arrivals in 2015 are estimate at approximately 193629 and 102.2% increase compare with arrivals of 9796 in 2014 and 137.17% increase 2013 compare with 2012. Most tourists are American, French, German, Dutch, Japanese, Thai and Chinese. Mandalay not only offers wonderful sights to behold, but also has a number of nearby attractions, most historical and fascinating. It is the major trading and communication center in northern and central Myanmar. Mandalay is strategically situated on important Ayeyarwaddy River and connects to India and China, Thailand and other parts of Southeast Asia via land routes.

Ministry of Hotel and Tourism has already opened two class for region guide in 2013 (Training No 1/2013) Total regional guide 120 and 2016 (Training No 21/2016) Total regional guide 112. Mandalay, as the center of Myanmar culture, was outstanding in the past, it holds the stage now; and it will continue to be a place of pride in the future. pt Flexible Incentives: Implement dynamic salary structures and non-monetary rewards, such as leadership opportunities and academic honors, to enhance talent retention and engagement.

The following figure (3.1) tourist arrival from 2012 shows the international to 2015.

Source: MOHT (2014 to 2016)

Table 3.1 Hotel and Guest House Growth in Mandalay

Year	Hotel and Guest House	Available Room
2014	142	5809
2015	168	6788
2016	183	7391

Source: MOHT (2014 to 2016)

Table (3.2) Monthly Tourist Arrival to Mandalay (2012 to 2014)

Month	2012	2013	2014	2015
Jan	14180	19376	22661	24685
Feb	15615	19754	23572	23904
Mar	11795	19420	17881	20999
Apr	6590	9314	10223	11677
May	5747	8331	9201	9731
Ju	4732	7602	8157	8129
Jul	6253	9820	10809	10351
Aug	8343	10775	10854	11051
Sep	7329	10182	9564	10681
Oct	9190	17671	17640	16441

Nov	20874	23488	24866	23966
Dec	16870	20462	24368	22014
Total	127718	175195	189796	193629

Source: MOHT, 2012–2015

According to the table 3.2, it can be significantly seen that tourist arrival in Mandalay is increasing year by year. Moreover, the number of the hotel and guest also go up.

4. Analysis on Factors of Tourist who Visited in Mandalay

This chapter analyzes the visitors' influencing factors of tourist who visited Mandalay. This chapter is based on 4 factors such as (1) environmental factors, (2) Socio-Economic factors, (3) Cultural factors and (4) Religious factors.

4.1 Profile of Respondents

Total 194 samples of tourists were interviewed and surveyed. Majority of tourists were surveyed at Mandalay International Airport Departure Waiting Lounge after they visited Mandalay and others were surveyed at Mandalay Hill after sunset. Table (4.1) shows the profile of surveyed tourists and include gender, age, occupation, travel expenses, regions and length of stay.

Gender: To avoid the bias, tourists were surveyed consistently in terms of their genders. Therefore, in the survey result, it can be seen that there was no significant difference between Respondent's Male sample size and Female sample size with the percentage of 49.5 percentage and 50.5 percentage respectively.

Age: Among five age range of tourists, the most surveyed tourists' age range was "between 26 and 35 years old" with the weight of 35.6 percent, the second most visited age range was "15–25 years old" with the weight of 32.5 percent and third most visited age range was "between 46 and 55 years old". The fourth most visited age range was "more than 55 years old" and the last one age range was "between 46–45 years old".

Occupation: From the result of the sample respondents, the most interviewed tourists were other professional with the percentage 26.8, followed by the students with the percentage of 25.3 and the teacher with the percentage of 12.9. For the survey, 8 types of occupation were interviewed and surveyed.

Travel Expenditure: According to the survey results, it can be seen that travel expense of "less than 300\$" with the percentage of 38.4 and followed by "301–600 \$" with the percentage of 27.3. From the result it can be found that although there is "above 3 days" took the highest position, travel expenditure is "less than 300\$".

Nationality: For analysis, 4 nationalities by regions of tourists were surveyed and

interviewed. For convenient way to communicate with Tourists during survey and interviewed, only those tourists who could speak in English were selected. Therefore, in the sample respondents, majority of sample sizes in Nationalities were Europe followed by Asia and American.

Length of Study: Among three types of Length of Stay, “Above 3 days” with the 41.8 percent and followed by “3days” length of stay with 30.9 percent. The last one is “less than 3 days” length of stay with 27.3 percent.

Table (4.1) Respondents’ Profile

		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	96	49.5
	Female	98	50.5
	Total	194	100.00

Age	15-25	63	32.5
	26-35	69	35.6
	36-45	14	7.2
	46-55	27	13.9
	>55	21	10.8
	Total	194	100.00
Occupation	Medical doctor	22	11.3
	Teacher	25	12.9
	Engineer	20	10.3
	Volunteer	6	3.1
	Business Owner	11	5.7
	Student		
	Retired	49	25.3
	Other	9	4.6
Total	52	26.8	
Total	194	100.00	
Travel expenditure	< 300\$	55	28.4
	301- 600 \$	53	27.3
	601-900 \$	24	12.4
	901-1200\$	13	6.7
	>1200 \$	49	25.3
	Total	194	100.00
Region	Europe Asia	162	83.5
	America Africa	20	10.3
		12	6.2
		0	0
Total	194	100.00	
Length of Stay	Less than 3 days		
	3Day	53	27.3
	Above 3 days	60	30.9
		81	41.8

	Total	194	100.00
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4.2 Factors influencing Tourist Visiting Mandalay

The visitors' influencing factors on visiting Mandalay were examined by 4 factors, such as factors influencing on environmental, factors influencing on socio-economic, and factors on cultural and factors on religious.

4.2.1 Factors influencing on Environmental

In this section, environmental influencing factors on tourist in Mandalay was analyzed by using five statements. The mean score of each statement is shown in the Table 4.2.

Table (4.2) Factor influencing on Environmental

No	Factor on Environmental	Mean value
1	Mandalay has a good climate.	3.22
2	Mandalay has a lot of beautiful scenery.	4.20
3	Mandalay's environment is clean and the pollution is acceptable.	2.79
4	Mandalay is safe to travel around.	4.18
5	Mandalay' population is right for the size of the city.	3.63
	Overall Mean	3.60

Table 4.2 demonstrates the respondents 'influencing factors on environment. According to the survey data, it can be examined that most of the international visitors have highly positive influencing on environment of Mandalay which got the overall mean value of 3.60. Among the 5 items relating to the environment factors, visitors strongly agree with the fact that Mandalay has a lot of beautiful scenery, with the mean value of 4.20.

Moreover, visitors strongly agree that Mandalay is safe to travel around with the mean value of 4.18. The mean value got 3.22 for the question of Mandalay has a good climate and the mean value 3.63 agree with the Mandalay' population is right for the size of the city. Additionally, the mean value goes down when the visitors are being asked about if the Mandalay' s environment is clean and the pollution is acceptable and got the mean value 2.79.

4.2.2 Factors influencing on Socio-Economic

In this section, socio-economic influencing factors on tourist in Mandalay was analyzed

by using five statements. The visitors influencing factors on socio-economic was being measured by statements such as: if the Mandalay in the service of transportation, accommodation, local food, tourist information and banking service. The mean score of each statement is shown in the Table 4.3.

Table (4.3) Factors influencing Socio-Economic

No	Factor on Socio-Economic	Mean value
1	The transportation (Bus/Train/ Boat/Car) in Mandalay was satisfactory.	3.45
2	My accommodation (Hotel) in Mandalay was good.	4.20
3	The local food was delicious.	4.06
4	I found the Tourist information (agency, tourist guide) easily.	3.44
5	The service of Banking and Money Exchange Service in Mandalay was convenient.	3.35
	Overall Mean	3.70

Table 4.3 demonstrates the respondents 'influencing factors on socio-economic in Mandalay. According to the survey data, it can be examined that most of the international visitors have highly positive influencing on the socio-economic of Mandalay which got the overall mean value of 3.70. From the table 4.3, it can be seen that the visitors strongly agree on the accommodation (Hotel) in Mandalay was good with the mean value of 4.20. Visitors also strongly agree that the local food was delicious as it got the mean value of 4.06. However, the mean value goes down slightly when the visitors are being asked about if the transportation (Bus/Train/ Boat/Car) in Mandalay was satisfactory, and if there was the Tourist information (agency, tourist guide) easily and if the service of Banking and Money Exchange Service in Mandalay was convenient as it got the mean value of 3.45, 3.44 and 3.35 each.

4.2.3 Factors influencing on Cultural

In this section, cultural influencing factors on tourist in Mandalay was analyzed by using five statements. The visitors influencing factors on cultural was being measured by statements such as: if the Mandalay is historically significant city, richness of culture and heritage, their traditional way of living style, information with historical sites and range of music

and dance. The mean score of each statement is shown in the Table 4.4.

Table (4.4) Factors influencing on Cultural

No	Factors on Cultural	Mean value
1	Mandalay is historically significant city.	4.37
2	Mandalay has richness of culture and heritage.	4.36
3	The people in Mandalay are still living their traditional way of life.	3.71
4	I gained a lot of information and experience from the historical sites.	3.66
5	I found a wide range of music & dance, theaters and troupes?	2.70
	Overall Mean	3.76

Table 4.4 demonstrates the respondents 'influencing factors on cultural in Mandalay. According to the survey data, it can be examined that most of the international visitors have highly positive influencing on the cultural of Mandalay which got the overall mean value of 3.76. From the table 4.4, it can be seen that the visitors strongly agree Mandalay is historically significant city with the mean value of 4.20. Secondly, the mean value of 4.36 expressed that visitor agree Mandalay has richness of culture and heritage. However, the mean value dropped slightly to 3.71 and 3.66 when visitors are being asked about the people in Mandalay are still living their traditional way of life and information and experience from the historical sites. The mean value decreased 2.70 when visitors are being asked about the wide range of music, dance, theaters and troupes.

4.2.3 Factors influencing on Religious

In this section, religious influencing factors on tourist in Mandalay was analyzed by using five statements. The visitors influencing factors on religious was being measured by statements such as: if visiting Mandalay is religious reason, it has a lot of holy sites, information with Meditation center, welcoming of pagodas and the center of Buddhist teaching. The mean score of each statement is shown in the Table 4.5.

Table (4.5) Factors influencing on Religious

No	Factor on Religious	Mean value
1	I visited Mandalay for religious reason.	1.71
2	Mandalay has a lot of holy sites.	4.38
3	Meditation centers in Mandalay need more information to attract international tourists.	3.71
4	The pagodas were welcoming to me.	4.24
5	Mandalay is the center of Buddhist Teaching.	3.59
	Overall Mean	3.53

So, it can be assumed that international visitor most influencing factor is Cultural. Factors influencing on environmental and factors influencing on socio-economic factors got the mean value of 3.60 and 3.70 respectively. However, the data stated that factors influencing on religious got only 3.53.

5. Conclusions

The summary of findings and suggestions on the study of visitor' influencing factor visited Mandalay are presented in this chapter. Moreover, this chapter also states some of the recommendations that need to be done for further research in the future.

5.1 Research Findings and Discussions

Most of the tourists are from Europe and the age range is between 26–35 years. Aside from Europe, it is also found that visitors from Asian and America. Over 91 percent of the respondents came to Mandalay as very first time. In case of occupation, other professional is the highest level and follow by students. In term of travel expense, it is found that about one fourth of the respondents use less than 300 \$. The visitors 'expense between 301 and 600 \$ got second level usage in Mandalay.

In general, it can be concluded that International Tourists have the strongly agree to all the factors. In comparing the different dimension of the tourist attraction area in Mandalay,

it is found that International Tourists have the strongly influencing by cultural factors. Consequently, International visitors have the second highest influencing factor is “Socio-economic factors”. On the other hand, it is also found that visitors have agreed on influencing factors of environment and religious factors. Moreover, from the analyzing result, more than 60 percent of the respondents have planned to come back Mandalay, whereas 32.5 percent of the respondents did not. However, over 97 percent of respondents mention that they will recommend others to visit Mandalay.

This study was conducted in order to figure out the different factors that influencing international tourists who visited in Mandalay. A total of 194 respondents were involved in this study. Over half of the respondents were female visitors and the rest of those were the male visitors.

5.2 Suggestions and Recommendation

study. Over half of the respondents were female visitors and the rest of those were the male visitBased on the findings of the surveyed data in the previous chapter, below are suggested recommendations. The majority of the respondents suggested that Mandalay should be a cleaner environment for the visitors to be pleased when they wander around the city. Only when Mandalay is clean and safe, most tourists would enjoy staying in Mandalay and touring around the city. Moreover, there should also have good public transportation for the tourists to ease going around the city as local bus has small network and not enough. Trains should be clean and comfortable. Toilets should also be spick and span, especially in tourist sites.

To attract more and more tourists to Mandalay, the government can make free activities like tour, online information, and guide on the sites, and transportation between main sites, hop-on and hop off, official hotel to find guides. To help the tourists coming to Mandalay, many good itineraries are necessity to better understand the local culture, talking to local people or monks, asking questions and having lunch together to exchange cultural information. There should also have signposts written to guide the tourists.

Concerned with Banking Sector, although ATM service is a great help for tourists, banks still exchange money with notes (i. e. accepting Euro and changing all kind of bank of notes). Thus, they should improve money exchange services. The better money exchange service, the more money can be circulated and as a result, the city would get more foreign income.

5.3 Limitations and Needs for Further Research

This study is only conducted influencing factors of international visitors having on Mandalay. However, in the future, if the situation was given, it is recommended to conduct in Bagan or Inlay Lake. Besides, the data for this study was collected in August, in the rainy season, so there were not many visitors as expected. Therefore, in the future, if the study could conduct around November or December, the peak tourism season in Myanmar, there may have different findings. Moreover, this study was ended only measuring on factors influencing on visitors. So that, in the future, one can also conduct the research that the main factors to be growth of Tourism in Mandalay.

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